

BioCompWaterClean Workshop

New applications in wastewater treatment
on the way to zero-waste technology

20-21 October, 2025, Novi Sad, Serbia

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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BIOCOMPWATERCLEAN WORKSHOP

NEW APPLICATIONS IN WASTEWATER
TREATMENT ON THE WAY TO ZERO-
WASTE TECHNOLOGY

Science and Technology Park Novi Sad
20-21 October, 2025, Novi Sad,
Serbia

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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WELCOME

On behalf of the Scientific and Organizing Committee, it is our great pleasure to warmly welcome you to the BioCompWaterClean Workshop, “New applications in wastewater treatment on the way to zero-waste technology”.

In a world facing the greatest challenges of current and future generations, innovation in water treatment and clean water is not just a scientific and professional task—it is also a social responsibility. In this context, and in line with current global demands and the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the BioCompWaterClean Workshop aims to add value by providing high-quality knowledge exchange that contributes particularly to SDG 4 (quality education) and SDG 6 (clean water and sanitation).

Multidisciplinary teams of researchers and experts in various fields of chemistry and technology will present at this two-day international workshop, sharing innovative methodologies and advances in processes for wastewater treatment, pollutant removal, new materials, and potential solutions for zero-waste technologies or waste material utilization and valorization. These efforts generate new resources to ensure the sustainable management of water and improve water quality.

Furthermore, the exchange of knowledge, best practices, and problem-solving ideas may drive new initiatives for further cooperation and joint projects.

Enjoy sharing your valuable time with us!

Prof. Dr. Slavica Ražić
BioCompWaterClean Project Leader

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PLENARY LECTURES

Đurđa Kerkez
Full Professor,
University of Novi Sad,
Faculty of Sciences
Republic of Serbia

Dr. Đurđa Kerkez is a full professor at the Faculty of Science, University of Novi Sad, at the Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection. Her scientific and research work is in the field of water quality, with a focus on improved wastewater treatment. She is the author and co-author of over 45 scientific papers in journals of international importance, as well as a large number of announcements at international and national conferences.

Scientific work is carried out through numerous international and national projects, as well as through cooperation projects with the economy. She managed the WasteWaterForce project from PROMIS, the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, as well as the CarbIrON project in cooperation with the Joint Research Center, and through them various innovative materials for wastewater treatment were developed. Currently, he manages the SmartWaterTwin project from Horizon Europe, which deals with the observation of wastewater through the framework of the circular economy, as well as Soil Sentinel, a citizen-science project exploring the potential for sewage sludge agricultural application.

She is the author and co-author of 11 textbooks, auxiliary textbooks and practicums, the most recent of which are the books Wastewater in the context of social challenges (2022) and Technological and resource aspects of the circular model of sludge management from water treatment (2024). Activities for both the scientific and wider social community are achieved through membership in the Serbian Chemical Society, the International Water Association - IWA and the Association for water technology and sanitary engineering. She is also the member of the steering committee of the Educational center for environmental protection EDEN.

A DECISION-MAKING FRAMEWORK FOR SUSTAINABLE SEWAGE SLUDGE MANAGEMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA: CIRCULAR ECONOMY PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract

The sewage sludge management is a key challenge for implementing circular economy principles in the wastewater sector. In the Republic of Serbia, the Regulation on the management of sludge from municipal wastewater treatment plants (Official Gazette RS, 103/2023) introduced stricter rules for sludge use, partly harmonized with the EU Sewage Sludge Directive (86/278/EEC) and the Circular Economy Action Plan. Despite this progress, selecting suitable treatment and reuse options remains complex, requiring decisions that balance environmental, technological, socio-economic, and regulatory factors. Decision-support framework for sludge management in the Republic of Serbia must integrate criteria such as sludge quantity and composition, pollutant and pathogen levels, energy and material recovery potential, regulatory compliance, cost-effectiveness, and social acceptance. Drawing on European best practices, the framework should compare key technological options including agricultural application, composting, anaerobic digestion, incineration, and advanced thermal treatments. Life-cycle assessment indicators such as greenhouse gas emissions, ecotoxicity, and nutrient recovery efficiency are also incorporated to ensure a comprehensive evaluation of environmental performance. The proposed framework supports evidence-based decisions that can transform wastewater treatment plants into resource recovery facilities. By aligning Serbian practice with EU circular economy principles, this approach enhances water security, promotes sustainable agriculture, and contributes to climate resilience in the Western Balkans.

Key words: *sewage sludge management, circular economy, resource recovery, regulatory framework*

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